

PROBLEMS IN READING COMPREHENSION AND THE WAY OF SOLVING THEM

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Annotation:

Learners learn differently, in different ways, and at different rates. Thus, in learning to read, some children need a little more of one thing while others need a bit more of another thing. Trying to push all learners through the same reading program will result in the slowed growth of some and the frustration of others the early stages it is important to make the task of learning to read as easy and interesting as possible. Students need a lot of practice before they are able to recognize words and phrases quickly, and even the most interesting reading book or textbook, gets boring if they have to read the same thing more than once. Learners of a foreign language, especially at elementary and intermediate levels, are rarely efficient readers in the foreign language. This has to do not only with deficiencies in linguistic knowledge, but also with the strategies employed in reading.

The article deals with the significance of reading in English. The practical usage and role of effective strategies in doing reading skills well.

The article describes general **characteristics of reading** and specific priorities in language. It indicates the importance of utilizing them and their meaning and shows the limit of them according to some particular reasons.

The purpose of article is to learn the ideas of great scholars around the world and define the difference between standard and nonstandard language units.

Introduction. Proficient reading depends on the ability to recognize words quickly and effortlessly. If word recognition is difficult, students use too much of their processing capacity to read individual words, which interferes with their ability to comprehend what is read.

Few would dispute the claim that comprehension is necessary in order for language acquisition to occur. In order to communicate effectively, learners must understand what is being said. To function successfully with a target language, learners depend upon their ability to comprehend the spoken and written word. Empirical studies have identified a positive relationship between listening ability and language acquisition as well as between reading ability and language acquisition.

During the last century comprehension lessons usually comprised students answering teachers' questions, writing responses to questions on their own, or both. The whole group version of this practice also often included "round robin reading" wherein teachers called on individual students to read a portion of the text (and sometimes following a set order). In the last quarter of the 20th century, evidence accumulated that the read-test methods assessed comprehension more than they taught it. The associated practice of "round robin" reading has also been questioned and eliminated by many educators.

Instead of using the prior read-test method, research studies have concluded that there are much more effective ways to teach comprehension. Much work has been done in the area of teaching novice readers a bank of "reading strategies" or tools to interpret and analyze text. There is not a definitive set of strategies, but common ones include summarizing what you have read, monitoring your reading to make sure it is still making sense, and analyzing the structure of the text (e.g., the use of headings in science text). Some programs teach students how to self-monitor whether they are understanding and provide students with tools for fixing comprehension problems.

Instruction in comprehension strategy use often involves the gradual release of responsibility, wherein teachers initially explain and model strategies. Over time, they give students more and more responsibility for using the strategies until they can use them independently. This technique is generally associated with the idea of self-regulation and reflects social cognitive theory, originally conceptualized by Albert Bandura. Comprehension is the ultimate goal of reading. However, there are a number of factors which may interfere with an individual's ability to comprehend text material.

Result. The most common single obstacle to text comprehension is decoding insufficiency. Simply put, if the student cannot decode accurately and automatically, comprehension will be compromised.

- When the student cannot "apprehend" or decode the word, meaning cannot be extracted.

- When the student cannot decode fluently and automatically, reading is slow and laborious and memory for read material is poor.

- When the student cannot decode and is taught to rely on "context cues" or to "guess" at words, comprehension is compromised.

A more subtle interference is an underlying problem with language comprehension or inferential thinking. Those with right-hemispheric or non-verbal learning disorders are typically proficient decoders or "word callers" who have little to no difficulty remembering the specific details of what they have read.

In this second category, the student typically does well in the early grades but begins to struggle academically in the higher grades when the demand for comprehension increases. Such students often begin to experience difficulty with test taking and lecture learning due to underlying deficits in complex comprehension of novel material and inferential thinking.

It is not until late elementary or middle school when the curriculum demands shift and the demand for complex comprehension increases. Students who start out strong but begin to experience learning difficulty in the higher grades should be evaluated for underlying deficits in comprehension.

Physiological vision problems, such as deficits in tracking and scanning, also interfere with comprehension of text. For example, if one were asked to read *Gone with the Wind* through a straw, the physical energy to perform the task would result in extreme fatigue, diminished attention and poor comprehension. Comprehension problems in this case would not be due to specific learning disability but to a sensory-based (and likely correctable) vision problem.

Lastly, psychological problems can also impair comprehension. Therefore, a comprehensive psychoeducational evaluation should be performed whenever a person experiences problems with text comprehension. Only through evaluation can one determine the root cause of difficulty and design appropriate intervention strategies.

Developing reading comprehension activities involves more than identifying a text that is "at the right level," writing a set of comprehension questions for students to answer after reading, handing out the assignment and sending students away to do it. A fully-developed reading activity supports

students as readers through pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading activities.

As you design reading tasks, keep in mind that complete recall of all the information in a text is an unrealistic expectation even for native speakers. Reading activities that are meant to increase communicative competence should be success oriented and build up students' confidence in their reading ability.

Conclusion. Reading is a skill that will empower everyone who learns it. They will be able to benefit from the store of knowledge in printed materials and, ultimately, to contribute to that knowledge. Good teaching enables students to learn to read and read to learn. The role of the teacher in the teaching-reading process should be of a companion rather than the boss. Teaching can be interesting and innovative if the efforts are put in to make learning an enjoyable experience.

Successful teaching is where effective learning takes place with the use of appropriate knowledge, the right emotion and accurate application of scientific devices. With consistent progress in science and technology and other areas of study, it is the duty of the teacher to adopt the best methods and employ the best devices to ensure rapid growth in the teaching process. Teachers must be aware of the progress that students are making and adjust instruction to the changing abilities of students. Both research and classroom practices support the use of a balanced approach in instruction. Because reading depends on efficient word recognition and comprehension, instruction should develop reading skills and strategies, as well as build on learners' knowledge through the use of authentic texts. Similarly, the most effective way of dealing with the problem of cultural meaning in texts is to encourage students to read by themselves, choosing subjects related initially to their own interests so that they bring motivation and experience to reading. As their understanding of other cultures and of unfamiliar views increases through reading, they will bring to their reading activities a gradually increasing capacity to understand the full meaning of texts.

When reading comprehension breaks down, different students need to find ways to repair their understanding. This is where the importance of knowing how to teach reading strategies come in, so as to facilitate the reading process and give students a clear sense of what they are reading. Students can become easily frustrated when they do not understand what they are reading and as a result, they become demotivated. A teacher needs to design and teach different strategies in order to help students close the gaps in their understanding. The ultimate challenge for the teacher is to know exactly which

strategy is useful and most beneficial to teach, since each student needs different strategies. This work in this respect, gives many strategies and a few general pointers for how to teach them.

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Bibliography:

1. Adams, Marilyn Jager. Beginning to Read: Thinking and Learning about Print, MIT Press, 1990, p. 27.
2. Alderson J.C. Reading in a foreign language: a reading problem or a language problem? // Alderson J.C. & Urquhart A.H. (eds.). Reading in a foreign language. London: Longman, 1984. P. 1-24.
4. Aldridge, M. (1989). Student questioning: A case for freshman academic empowerment. RTDE, 5 (2), 17-24.
5. Anisfeld, M. (1987). A course to develop competence in critical reading of empirical research in psychology. Teaching of Psychology, 14, 224-227.
6. Collins, N. & Smith, C. (1990). Role of metacognition in reading to learn. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 333 386)
8. Carrell P.L., Devine J. & Eskey D.E. (eds.). Interactive Approaches to Second Language Reading. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1988.
9. Chamberlain, K. & Burrough, S. (1985). Techniques for teaching critical reading. Teaching of Psychology, 12, 213-215.
10. Clarke M.A. The short circuit hypothesis of ESL reading - or when language competence interferes with reading performance // Carrell P.L., Devine J. & Eskey D.E. (eds.). Interactive Approaches to Second Language Reading. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1988. P. 114-124.
11. www.ziyonet.uz
12. www.edu.uz
13. www.pedagog.uz
14. <http://www.pdf-finder.com/The-importance-of-reading-English-for-EFL-language-learners-can-not-be.html/>

